

BASAGLIA'S "ANTI-PSYCHIATRY" INTER- PRETED THOUGHT GALTUNG'S DEFINITION OF A(N INNER) CONFLICT

di Antonino Drago

Abstract

Present communication shows that Franco Basaglia's intellectual path from a positivist conception to an existentialist and Heideggerian conception of psychiatry corresponds to an adding to the only dimension of objective Behavior (B) which the traditional psychiatry saw in a mentally ill person, two more dimensions: C (contradiction, feelings, human relationships) and A (assumptions, pre-conceptions) so that without knowing it Basaglia shared Johan Galtung's representation of a(n inner) conflict as an A-B-C. Through Galtung's definition a mental illness is characterized as a C which determines the personal behavior B, whereas A is unconscious. On the other hand, an institution is characterized as an A which determines a person's behavior B (also within his collective actions) by suffocating his C. Moreover, through the A-B-C the psychoanalytical method is characterized as a process of growing awareness of both Patient and Analyst; this process is performed by a specific cooperation of two actors during a session: Patient's B is the soft behavior of remembering dreams, while Analyst's B is silent; moreover, A is silent in the former one, while is active in the latter one; C is verbally expressed by the former one while is virtually simulated by the latter one. In such a way they together make experience of the inner conflict at issue as they were only one person with his own A-B-C. It is shown that the decisive steps of this therapeutic process are based on a clever use of negations, culminating in a translation from a virtual world to a real world; this translation consists in an Analyst's application of the principle of sufficient reason, suitably subjected to two reality constraints, to the conclusion of his elaborated theory of Patient's ill. This kind of therapeutic process of a Patient parallels what Basaglia performed for overcoming the forced life inside an authoritarian institution (asylum). I will interpret the conflict between a person with mental illness and an institution, where institution's interaction with a patient is interpreted as a triadic conflict, indicated by an A-B-C. Basaglia's general attitude is at last discussed.

Keywords: Franco Basaglia, Beyond positivistic psychiatry, Galtung's definition of a conflict, Interpretation of the psycho-analytic process, Interpretation of the de-institutionalization.

1. *Introduction*

The leading idea of the following analysis is Johan Galtung's general definition of a conflict. A conflict is an A-B-C, where A means Assumptions, B behavior and C (inner) contradictions.¹ First of all, that means that a conflict has to be understood through three independent dimensions, which in Galtung's writings are defined in various ways but (as a previous paper fixed them²) are substantially the following ones: A assumptions, B Behavior and C interior contradiction

The triadic nature of a conflict gives reason of the lack of past Western theories on it; since Greek's times, Western thinking was confined to conceive single ideas or at most two contra posed ideas (e.g. true/false, good/evil, proletariat/bourgeoisie, etc.), never three ideas coalescing into one idea (apart the idea of Christian Trinity, which however was almost useless owing to its unavoidable oxymora). This triadic thinking is a novelty to which Western thinking and philosophy were not prepared by previous elaborations.

Galtung's definition covers all kinds of conflicts, ranging from the wars (e.g. Clausewitz' theory of war) to the social conflicts (e.g. Marx' theory of class struggle), the interpersonal conflicts and the inner conflicts (e.g. Freud psychoanalysis)³.

¹ J. GALTUNG, *Peace by Peaceful Means*, Sage, London 1996, chap. 2, 1.

² A. DRAGO, *Improving Galtung's A-B-C to a scientific theory of all kinds of conflicts*, in «Ars Brevis. Anuari de la Càtedra Ramon Llull Blanquenra», XXI, 2016, pp. 56-91.

³ A. DRAGO, S. MARADEI, *Getting out the vagueness of medicine: the four English names for disease*, in «US-China Education Review A», 14, 2024, pp. 566-577.

Through Galtung's definition one characterizes a mental illness as a C which determines the personal behavior B, whereas A is either silent or stray. On the other hand, one characterizes an institution as an A which determines a person's behavior B (also his actions within collective groups) by suffocating his C. These ideas are easily recognized as representing both Franco Basaglia's elaboration on mental illness and the leading ideas of the movement for a new treatment of the persons confined inside psychiatric hospitals.

In sect. 2 I will present the evolution of Basaglia's thinking from his positivistic studies to a more wide horizons which correspond to his taking-over of a viewpoint corresponding to Galtung's definition of an inner conflict as composed by three dimensions, A-B-C. In sect. 3 I will present a fresh interpretation of the psycho-analysis process as modeled by the triadic definition of the A-B-C. In sect. 4 I will suggest an interpretation of Basaglia's evolution from his previous phenomenological viewpoint to his adhesion to also a political (Marxist) one. In sect. 5 I will interpret the conflict between a person with mental illness and an institution, where the institution's action and interaction with a patient is interpreted as a triadic conflict indicated by an A-B-C. Basaglia's general attitude is at last discussed.

2. Evolution of Basaglia's thinking from positivism to an open view implicitly adhering to Galtung's definition of a conflict

Owing to the dominant culture of Basaglia's time his education to the therapeutic care of mental illness was of a positivistic kind. The symptoms were decisive for both characterizing the illness and deciding the borderline between malady and sanity. In the first case the destiny of a mental ill person was marked irreversibly: an internment inside an asylum for badly surviving together with other persons suffering all kinds of mental ills, without any hope of a change of life, apart an almost miraculous recovery.

In other terms, being four the basic names of a malady in English language⁴, the mental ill was essentially treated as a sickness; this notion describes the concept of malady from the viewpoint of society which through its public health institutions takes care of the sick person.

“Sickness” refers [malady] to the social dimension: the ability to meet obligations of group living. It is the result of being defined by others as “unhealthy”. It generally results from having one’s failure to meet social obligations defined by others as the result of disease or illness⁵.

Sickness is a social identity. It is the poor health or the health problem(s) of an individual defined by others with reference to the social activity of that individual⁶.

Point of view: of society. *Keywords:* social status, social role of sick person, socio-health system *Idea:* Anomalies in the structure and functioning of body system.

Being at fault for the structure of social life. Inability to fulfill social obligations. Reduction of participation in organized life, with consequences for the social relationships of others. Evidence of a deviation from the social norm. Statement of malady given by others. Social acknowledgement of being ill. Social objectification of a person’s malady as qualified by health care medicine. A specific case of lack of social participation contemplated by the employment contract⁷.

⁴ A. DRAGO, *Improving Galtung’s A-B-C to a scientific theory of all kinds of conflicts*, cit.

⁵ A. C. TWADDLE, *Sickness and the Sickness Career: Some Implications*, in L. Eisenberg, A. Kleinman (eds.), *Clinical social science, The Relevance of social science for medicine*, D. Reidel, Dordrecht 1981, pp. 111-133, p. 112.

⁶ ID., *Disease, Illness and Sickness revisited*, in *Disease, Illness and Sickness: Three Central Concepts in the Theory of Health*, a cura di A. C. Twaddle, L. Nordenfel, Linköping, 1994, pp. 37-53, p. 40.

⁷ A. DRAGO, S. MARADEI, *Getting out the vagueness of medicine: the four English names for disease*, cit., p. 572.

Let us compare the mental ill intended as a sickness with Johan Galtung's notion of a conflict as an A-B-C⁸. First of all notice that the positivistic conception of a mental ill objectively recognizes the symptoms of the malady of a deviant behavior (referred to an abstract idea or even a mind's lesion), i.e. as only a B. No attention is devoted by the positivistic conception to A, i.e. the premises of this behavior, as well as C, i.e. the inner feelings experienced by a ill person. According to this conception the B is enough for qualifying in society a mental ill person and for deciding his forced exclusion from the social life, by confining him into an asylum. In sum, also for a positivistic conception a mental ill person is mainly a social problem decided by an authoritative institution; and a "sane" society has to reject a mental ill person as including "foolish" aspects.

Going beyond the B of the positivistic view Basaglia, through the phenomenology of Husserl, Heidegger, Biswanger, Minkowski etc., recuperated as an essential dimension the C of a mental ill person. Here, Basaglia met the great difficulty of a reconstruction of a scientific attitude capable to take into account the entire personality of a patient, whose inner world was devastated. No longer for Basaglia the subjectivity of a mental ill person is a dark hole, but it is dealt as an essential component of his interaction with the therapist. That means that the feelings of a mental ill person are not only admissible but constitutes an essential part of the cure. Which is conducted by the therapist according to an attitude not of detachment, from the outside of the patient, but by sharing as much as possible the feelings communicated by the patient

⁸ Actually, Galtung had conceived this triadic thinking already in 1972. In a paper devoted to epistemology (J. GALTUNG, *Empiricism, Criticism, Constructivism. Three Approaches to Scientific Activity*, in «Synthese», XXIV, 1972, pp. 343-372) science itself was conceived as a triangle, whose vertices are Data, Theory and Values and whose sides are Empiricism, Criticism and Constructivism. By ignoring the remaining parts considered as extraneous to a scientific attitude the positivistic attitude reduces this triangle to Empiricism and Data. The deep gap between the two conceptions manifests the deep difficulty met by the scholars of this time wanting to exit out the Empiricism-Positivism.

and guessed by the therapist. So that these two distinct persons live in common as much as possible a same C. In such a way their interaction is not governed by the rationality of the dominant scientific epistemology; to which Basaglia addressed harsh criticisms:

science is crazier than madness because the scientific thinking undergoes the same process as *dénudation*, which Basaglia talks about, continuing Minkowski, regarding schizophrenic thinking. Thought is «stripped, enucleated, stripped of its part unreality that exists in it. Real and unreal cannot but coexist and integrate, because stripping one of the other will take place or a rich delirious flourishing or a hyperconcrete, a hyperrational that ends with the represent nothing more than a caricature of real⁹.

This rationality is based on the dichotomy True/False referring to only ontological beings, approximately instantiated by the things of the real world. This rationality presents itself as an unavoidable one. The entire society conforms itself to this rationality, so that a simple deviation from it, presented by the life of a mental ill person, is a manifestation of a malady; on its hand the social life, in order to assure its best working, has to exclude the ill person from it. It is this kind of rationality that governs the positivistic attitude.

Instead Basaglia did not believe in the appropriateness of this kind of logic for understanding the therapeutic interaction, which rather has to be based on the discovery of the logic of emotions and idealities, even if the mental ill person experiences them through non-standard models of reality, which therefore may be described through a different kind of logic from the usual one.

Actually, in science some theories (e.g. Lazare Carnot's differential calculus in 1787, Sadi Carnot's thermodynamics in 1824, Lobachevski's geometry in 1840) introduced non-standard models describing non-real

⁹ Quoted in M. COLUCCI, P. DI VITTORIO, *Franco Basaglia*, Mondadori, Milano 2001, p. 44.

worlds that however lead to discover new schemes of comprehension of the subjects at issue. It is remarkably that this introduction of non-standard models is governed by an important non-classical logic, the intuitionist one¹⁰. This point will be considered in details in the following.

In sum, Basaglia has the great merit of having overcome through his therapeutic process and his path suggested by him for a new social life the Italian positivistic attitude which had locked up patient's personality inside an iron cage of only objective data; he has introduced new ways of understanding this personality. But, given the poor general culture of his time he achieved no more than philosophical and subjective conceptions of these subjects, not a structural definition of the kind of malady at issue. On the other hand, no one of the (anti)-psychiatric movement of his time discovered a link between the novelties and structural Galtung's definition of a conflict.

3. *Freud's theory and Galtung's definition*

Since directly or indirectly all therapists referred to Freud's theory it is important to recognize that it is well-illustrated by the A-B-C of the inner conflict to be cared.

More than a century ago, by breaking a long tradition of metaphysical conceptions of a person's interior, Freud started a therapy of inner conflicts. After him, a century elapsed before Galtung defined in general terms a conflict. Freud substantially anticipated Galtung's definition of a conflict that occurs according to three independent dimensions. Conversely, Freud's theory is easily illustrated through an A-B-C. The three dimensions parallel the three theoretical objects described in a personified way by Freud, respectively: A is represented by the Super-Ego, B by the Ego, C by the Id. The first two parallelisms are manifest; the third,

¹⁰ A. DRAGO, *Pluralism in Logic. The Square of opposition, Leibniz's principle and Markov's principle*, in *Around and Beyond the Square of Opposition*, ed. J.-Y. Béziau, D. Jacqueline, Birkhauser, Basel 2012, pp. 175-189.

C, is the result of Id's drives which are in contradiction among themselves as well as with both Super-Ego and Ego.

3.1 *The roles played by the Patient and the Analyst*

First of all, Freud's therapy adds to a person suffering an inner conflict (the Patient) one more person (the Analyst); in other words, it doubles the person taking care of the conflict of the original system. In terms of persons, this is the least generalization, the adjunction of one person. Why? Because an adjunction simplifies the search for a solution of the problem - as Lazare Carnot suggested it about a mathematical system: "To generalize is to simplify"¹¹. Once a solution is obtained, in order to come back to the original system, being equipped with the wanted solution, one has to eliminate in a formally correct way the adjunction.

In the past several founders of scientific theories of not-paradigmatic kind (Lazare Carnot in mechanics, geometry and calculus, S. Carnot in thermodynamics, Lobachevsky in non-Euclidean geometry, Galois in his algebraic theory, Klein in group theory of geometries, Einstein in special relativity, etc.) have applied this method¹². Also the first non violent person in Europe, Aldo Capitini, applied in order to found his philosophical theory of non-violence¹³. In the case of Freud's therapy the

¹¹ L. CARNOT: *Dissertation sur la théorie de l'infini mathématique* (1781), in *Lazare Carnot Savant*, ed. C. C. Gillispie, Princeton U.P., Princeton 1971, p. 258.

¹² A. DRAGO, "Pluralism in Logic. The Square of opposition, Leibniz's principle, cit., pp. 175-189. This paper presents all those details of the above mentioned theories which will be referred to in the following.

¹³ A. CAPITINI: *L'avvenire della dialettica*, in *Il messaggio di Aldo Capitini*, ed. G. Cacioppo, Lacaita, Manduria 1969, pp. 187-194; A. DRAGO, *Peace Profile: Aldo Capitini*, in «Peace Review», XXVI.3, 2014, pp. 434-439, sect. 3. Also Galtung suggests to look for a non-violent conflict resolution by means of an adjunction; he suggests as an instance the well-known tale of the three sons receiving an heredity of 17 camels to be partitioned in the proportions of $\frac{1}{2}$, $\frac{1}{3}$ and $\frac{1}{9}$. The rebus is solved by the adjunction of one camel, which at the end of the divisions, performed on 18 camels, can be freed.

adjunction is exactly aimed at making easier the search of the solution of the illness. Once the wanted solution is obtained, the (interaction with the) Analyst is abandoned by the (healed up) Patient¹⁴.

But what is this interaction? Freudian therapy rationalizes a component of the therapy, i.e., the transfer between Patient and Analyst. In order to explain this process of resolution I double Galtung's triad A-B-C in correspondence to previous adjunction of one person. Now we have to think through a complex system of several (six) dimensions in their cooperative representation of an *a priori* obscure process. However, under a closer inspection the situation is not so much cumbersome as it appears at glance. In his interaction with the Patient the Analyst actually suppresses its B, apart his speaking in a gentle way, so much to never hurt or shocking the Patient. In other words, the Analyst's B is reduced to suggesting merely soft ideas, which could be considered by the Patient as coming not from a different person, but from himself, like any new idea which born in his mind. Patient's B instead is present; but only as a plain behavior, since he merely talks on his unconscious life, as dreaming and similar experiences; and moreover Patient does it without responsibilities or even without awareness; in other words, and under another viewpoint, Patient's A is made at all silent.

Instead Analyst's A is very present; it put in place his professional preparation and personal assumptions, his human experience of a mature person; and it interiorizes the contents of Patient's verbal communications, elaborates these contents, takes decisions on how to elaborate them in order to eventually suggest to the Patient (no more than) some hints, aimed at opening his mind to productive novelties. Moreover, along the time of a session Analyst's A forces his C to concur with Patient's C (the two C's are different only outside a session; in particular,

¹⁴ More details on this method are presented by A. DRAGO, E. ZERBINO, *Sull'interpretazione metodologica del discorso freudiano*, in «*Rivista di Psicologia, Neurologia e Psichiatria*, LVII, 1996, pp. 539-566, sect. 2f.

Analyst's C re-gains its freedom to interact with his other two dimensions B and A in order elaborate the material gathered inside a session).

Let us compare the two actors through their three dimensions. We see that, in the absence of Patient's A, Analyst's A plays a dominant role in orienting the interaction, although Analyst interacts rarely and in a very soft way. In particular, their mutual communication is highly unbalanced: while the Analyst is almost silent, the colloquial behavior (B) of the Patient dominates the scene of their interaction; it occasions a lot of subjects of conversation through which the two persons interact. Notice that Patient's contribution is very great, but only occasionally relevant to the final result, the recovery; whereas Analyst's contribution is small, but is so much important to be decisive in addressing their interaction.

By superimposing the triads A-B-C of the two actors, we obtain a unique C (coming from the amalgamation of both C's), a unique B (i.e. the behavior of Patient's talking) and a unique A (i.e. Analyst's one). In sum, the kind of interaction of these two persons defines an intimate, visceral symbiosis of two distinct persons through their common sharing a same C, plus Patient's B and Analyst's A. In total, these three dimensions shape one "augmented person". In other words, during a session the therapeutic process is experienced by two persons, but it works as a living experience of one person, i.e. the augmented one; therefore, the therapeutic process does not exit out the life of a human being. Indeed, by this superposition of the two A-B-C's the joined two persons gain a mutual and calm cooperation, encouraging them to have a mutual transfert of feelings and even love (C). This fact guarantees that the therapy works as a sane human process.

3.2 *The crucial role of the doubly negated propositions within Patient–Analyst’s verbal communication*

Fortunately we can exploit a very important Freud’s reflection about his therapeutical method, i.e. a short paper titled *Die Verneinung*¹⁵. There, Freud explains that a linguistic negation represents an affective negation, i.e. a Patient’s repression of a psychical trauma, which sometimes slipping out inner repression emerges into the objective world: «The negation is already a taking into account of the repressed trauma... yet it is not a [conscious] acceptance of it». Therefore Freud invites Analyst to catch each negation of Patient’s talking; for instance the following negation: «It is not my mother (that I wanted to kill). From it Freud deduces an affirmative proposition: “Thus (German: *Also*), it is the mother».

This “Thus” is a strange logical implication, because it is not a single deduction – and even less a purely deductive process - which can address to a sure recognition of Patient’s trauma or whatsoever is at the origin of his illness. Moreover, Freud has no evidence for supporting the affirmative conclusion, because not all Patient’s negations refer to his subconscious. In general terms, a deduction of classical logic based on the bivalence principle (true/false in a mirror way) cannot at all deal with an idea composed by three dimensions, as a conflict is. Therefore, at this step of the therapeutic process the Analyst is allowed to advance no more than a suspect. I conclude that this Freud’s “deduction” was incorrect and that for this reason in the subsequent part of his paper Freud missed to explain through which kind of investigation an Analyst is capable to transform a suspect into a productive hypothesis for recovering Patient’s well-being.

The conclusion, being a suspect; has rather to be correctly represented by a doubly negated proposition: «It is not true that he did not

¹⁵ S. FREUD, *Die Verneinung*, in ID., *The Standard Edition of the Complete Psychological Works of Sigmund Freud*, London, 1953-1974, vol. 19, pp. 233-240).

want to kill his mother». It is remarkable that the original text of each of the above-mentioned scientific theories includes a lot of DNPs; also for this reason in the above I suggested that the proposition to be built on Patient's proposition is rather a DNP. Moreover, it is the triadic nature of a conflict that obliges the Analyst to make use of non-classical logic.

Notice that the latter proposition is Patient's one with the addition of one more negation.¹⁶ Let us remark that at Freud's time no mathematical logician gave relevance to a doubly negated proposition. Yet, later it gained great relevance because it was proved that the failure of the double negated law («Two negations do not affirm») constitutes the best borderline between intuitionist logic and classical logic¹⁷. Hence, when in a text a doubly negated proposition does not correspond in meaning to its corresponding affirmative proposition, it represents a case of failure of the double negation law of classical logic and therefore it belongs to intuitionist logic (DNP).

Actually, the crucial problem of Freud's method is subsequent his illustration of the adjunction of a negation: How Analyst can *reason* about a suspect about a Patient's trauma? (It is not a valid objection that a reasoning is impossible because the content of a DNP is not circumscribed in a clear-cut way; instead, such is the nature of an inductive reasoning of the Analyst, like the kind of reasoning within all the above theories).

¹⁶ This addition does not represent a Hegelian move. In Hegel's dialectic one starts from an affirmative (term, or) proposition, then negates it and at last adds one more negation in order to obtain a transcending proposition of the previous two; i.e. he gives reality to all three propositions (respectively: affirmative, negative and doubly negated). Instead, here both affirmative and negative propositions are only partially true; whereas the doubly negated proposition expresses a reliable suspect, to be then elaborated in order to eventually grasp something on the reality.

¹⁷ D. PRAWITZ, P.-E. MALMNAAS, *A survey of some connections between classical intuitionistic and minimal logic*, in *Contributions to Mathematical Logic*, ed. by H. A. Schmidt, K. Schütte, H.-J. Thiele, North-Holland, Amsterdam 1968, pp. 215-229.

Surely, an Analyst has to mutually compare all the elements in his possession in order to theorize Patient's interior situation and then answer to the following question: Does my accumulation of elements lead to compose a consistent framework with Patient's personality and his illness? Surely, Analyst cannot decide about the mutual consistency of these elements by deriving them from assured axioms, which here are lacking. And even if some fixed points there existed, an Analyst cannot attribute his logical deductions to Patient's life, since latter's mind is disturbed by illness.

Rather, the above mentioned scientific theories show that several DNPs may be linked together into an *ad absurdum* argument (AAA). Also Freud's paper implicitly suggested an AAA, although not well formulated. The last propositions of this paper are aimed at validating previous analysis of the role played by negation in his previous analysis. These last propositions may be translated as follows: previous analysis is valid; otherwise we have to admit that a negation would come out the Id; that is absurd, because never this event has been discovered. This proposition constitutes *Freud's methodological principle* (it is comparable to a celebrated principle of theoretical mechanics, i.e. the impossibility of a motion without an end).

Notice that in an AAA about a Patient's life the absurd is represented neither by a general, unique absurdity, nor by a single method to decide the absurdity of something at issue, but by a specific absurdity of very strange situations which are peculiar to Patient's illness. This specific absurdity characterizes a kind of logic which is weaker than not only classical logic, but also intuitionist one: it is the minimal logic¹⁸. This characterization of the peculiar kind of logic in Freud's analyses gives reason of one more difficulty met by scholars wanting to accurately understand the logical content of the transfer: minimal logic is scarcely known.

The conclusion of an AAA, again a DNP, may work as a premise of a next AAA and so these AAAs compose a chain of arguments (as in

¹⁸ J.-B. GRIZE, *Logique*, in *Logique et connaissance scientifique, Encyclopédie de la Pléiade*, ed. J. Piaget, Gallimard, Paris 1970, pp. 206-210.

history of science occurred in some scientific theories: Sadi Carnot's thermodynamics 1824, Lobachevsky non-Euclidean geometry 1840, Kolmogorov's theory of intuitionist logic 1932). Hence, Analyst can reason through a chain of AAAs in order to step-by-step build an interpretative framework. The historical novelty of Freud's method is to have made this kind of reasoning a systematic practice scattered in innumerable therapies which are peculiar to very different kinds of illnesses.

3.3 The final step: Analyst's application of Leibniz' principle of sufficient reason

At last a chain of AAAs obtains again a DNP. The theoretical development of each of the above-mentioned scientific theories presents as next step an application of the principle of sufficient reason. In past time its applications suggested also bizarre metaphysical results. Yet, a scientist (Markov, founding the theory of constructive numbers) declared that this application is valid in the case the final DNP fulfils two constraints: to be the conclusion of an AAA and decidable¹⁹. Let us investigate whether these constraints apply to Freud's method. 1) The final DNP is derived from an AAA: a correct Analyst's reasoning obtains a conclusion from some AAAs concerning his knowledge of Patient and previous Freud's basic methodological principle. 2) It is decidable: surely the material of a dream cannot be decided: rather, Analyst has to refer the suggestion of Patient's dreams to past actions and traumas of Patient's life.

After having elaborated some AAAs constituting a consistent theoretical reasoning on Patient's (disturbed) personality, Analyst applies the principle of sufficient reason to his final DNP. This translation implies a change of the kind of logic, from the non-classical one to the

¹⁹ A. DRAGO, *A Scientific Re-assessment of Leibniz's Principle of Sufficient Reason*, in *The Dialogue between Sciences, Philosophy and Engineering. New Historical and Epistemological Insights. Homage to Gottfried W. Leibniz 1646-1716*, ed. by R. Pisano et al., College Publications, London, 2017, pp. 121-140.

classical one, from an inductive search to deductive derivations²⁰. Indeed, the application of this principle translates the final DNP into the corresponding affirmative proposition, which, only because it is affirmative, can be tested with reality, i.e. to test whether it matches with Patient's past and present life. Now Analyst reasons no longer in an inductive way, rather in a deductive way in order to explain from his reasoned hypothesis all what Patient has said within the sessions about his past life.

The above illustrated chain of AAAs manifests the highly speculative nature of Analyst's work of interpretation; moreover, his professional capability mainly consists in choosing the best moment for applying the principle of sufficient reason. At last he obtains a scientific theory, although of a specific field of experiences, those pertaining to the inner world of one person only. In conclusion, I stress that Analyst's work is the result of not only human empathy towards Patient, but mainly reasoning according to a sophisticated method, which however was already suggested centuries ago by some scientific theories.

Basaglia perceived the limits of many psychiatric methods, mainly those applied inside the asylums. But unfortunately, he lacked of clear criteria through which to choose a therapeutic method which surely represented the best one for him. As a result, he did not dispose of a certain professional therapeutic method to follow in his tireless work for liberating the mental ill persons.

4. *Basaglia's transition from a phenomenological attitude to a political viewpoint*

In the literature it is debated the question whether there is a continuity between Basaglia's great effort of overcoming his positivist education by referring to Husserl, Heidegger, Minkowski etc. and the next

²⁰ It is easily proved through the table of M. DUMMETT, *Elements of Intuitionism*, Claredon, Oxford 1977, p. 29.

political commitment to a political conception of both the mental ill person and the asylums²¹. His political commitment occurred in a time Italian students discovered the relevance of Marxist analysis of society, the consequent politics and the commitment with the politics of worker class interrelated by its institutional representatives, i.e. leftist trade union and communist party.

Let us remark that it was Marx that first introduced a theory of the conflict within society (although a particular kind of it, the historical class conflict). It is not commonly considered that Marx' theory, surely concerning a conflict is well represented by Galtung's A-B-C.

First of all, let us remark that Marx' theory considers the social conflict as performed by three actors - i.e. capital, bourgeoisie and worker class. They are the representatives of the three Galtung's dimensions: the capital represents A, bourgeoisie's rule B, worker class suffering the social contradictions C.

In addition, let us remark that Marx offered three distinct illustrations of class conflict: a subjective illustration (*Parisian Manuscripts*), an objective illustration (*Capital* and *Anti-Duehring*) and the motivational illustration (*Fragment on Machines*).

Fig. Marx' three illustrations of class conflict

²¹ M. COLUCCI, P. DI VITTORIO, *Franco Basaglia*, cit., chap. 3: *La svolta politica*.

The book *Parisian manuscripts* constitutes Marx subjective illustration of the conflict between proletarians and the bourgeoisie; yet he ignores society's structures (e.g. bureaucracy, technology, war, ecology, etc.) as Marx theorized in his youth. Instead, by reducing the image of reality to an economicist picture, the book *Das Kapital* (and even more the book *Anti-Duebring*) constitutes Marx' objective illustration of the conflict between proletarians and capital. At last, the *Fragment on machines* constitutes an illustration of the long-term strategy of the two dominant social powers, bourgeoisie and capital; this writing ignores the role played by the proletariat, which however in previous writing Marx had conceived as the social actor breaking this strategy. Let us remark that each representation refers to two actors only; in other terms, Marx's three writings constitute three different ways for acquiring partial consciousness of this great social conflict that Marx attempted to describe. In other words, Marx did not achieve a complete, ultimate theory of this conflict. As a matter of fact, he was satisfied by only the first volume of *The Capital*, which was the one edited during his life.

However, Marx' theory, as a whole, constituted the closest approximation to an adequate representation of this great social conflict, certainly much more close than bourgeois' ideology which represented society through idealistic notions (freedom, progress, etc.) and saw the social conflict in subjective terms only C: e.g. rebels, evil minded, etc. Even more inadequate was capitalists' picture of the only one conflict they recognized; by ignoring both subjective (C) and motivational (A) aspects of population, they only took into account the social resistance (B) to the unbounded growth of capital's social development.

By implicitly referring to the entirety of Galtung's theory of a conflict as an A-B-C, Basaglia's effort for recuperating a global vision of the mental ill person was fascinated by Marx's illustration of the more comprehensive within the entire society, surely a global conflict including all conflicts at all lower social levels. In addition, this theory appeared to him as a program for a short-term historical transition to a new society,

managed by the representatives of the deprived social groups to which almost all his patients pertained. Furthermore, Marxism promised that this transition had build over again new social institutions, among which one had to consider also the awful asylums of his time, that Basaglia wanted to eliminate. In sum, Basaglia could recognize in the Marxist theory the term *ad quem* of his subjective and phenomenological search for a global theory of both the personal transformation he wanted to elicit in the mental ill persons and the social transformation of the asylums into new therapeutic communities.

Yet, his adhesion to Marx' theory implied contradictions inside his thinking.

According to Marx, the historical conflict between capitalism and worker class will be solved with the suppression of the capitalism; this suppression will occur when the exploited class will become aware of the historical development of the society as a whole. Marx wanted to grow up the consciousness of the worker class («...unite!», not «arm themselves!»), i.e. to promote a conversion of the worker class (from its constituting a class *per se* to a class *in se*) generating almost automatically the elimination of the bourgeoisie. But his followers conceived this gigantic social transformation in the usual instinctual terms, which at last appealed to the arms, although this violent solution diverges from the process of an inner transformation of the working class²². The subsequent almost military trend followed by the workers movement was so compelling that a strict discipline was introduced, not only with respect to the trade Unions (reduced by Lenin to the “drive belt” of Communist Party's decisions) but also the personal life crushed in function of the achievement of collective targets. Instead Basaglia's culture was based on the main novelty of 19th Century's work for the resolution of inner conflicts: therapists' basic activity looks for a positive solution looked for through a constructive a dialogue performed inside cooperative relationships.

²² In fact, Marxist movement ignored the social non-violent means for solving conflicts; these means have been suggested by Gandhi just after Marx.

Moreover, the Marxist strategy condemned all bourgeoisie' social institutions as pertaining to a historical stage of development to be overcome as soon as possible. This attitude led to devalue any attitude for merely reforming the asylums, for rather proceeding as fast as possible to their dissolutions. Basaglia maintained this radical attitude by rejecting any reformist program, although he well-knew that any social change requires a series of steps along a not short span of time.

In addition, the great widening of the social horizon given by Marx' theory generated some deep contradictions generated by two apparently irreducible polarities: the extreme case of personal turbulent feelings of a mental ill person and the long-term strategic program of the worker class as the structural agent of mankind history. The gap between these two polarities was a boundless space where no previous attempt of conciliation of the two polarities was given. Also at the intermediate social level the political definitions of the professional therapeutic roles (of the therapist and the nurse) gave very difficult problems. Basaglia tried to improve the consciousness of a therapist conceived as performing professional work acting inside a set of great social forces and during a historical transition process. His criticism to the positivist attribution of only a B to a patient was now extended to the power system which attributes pre-established professional roles which as a fact make worthless all subjective goodwill initiatives for changing the situation. No surprise if his analyses, the most advanced ones among the Marxist analyses of a professional role, were very suffered and at last they led to labyrinthine discussions, whose conclusions were no more than temptative. However, their great merit was to elicit much similar analyses performed by the professionals of many different institutions.

Even more deep was the theoretical contradiction generated by Marxist movement in Basaglia's thought. Marx wanted to reason through dialectical processes which had to turn over the feet Hegel's dialectics standing on the head of a theological thinking. But, he was unsuccessful. Later Marxist movement pursued the effort for changing Hegel's dialectics into a clear logical process; but again it was unsuccessful, whereas the temporary demands of a harsh politics of collision with

bourgeoisie obliged it to assume a pragmatic attitude in agreement of the tradition of western politics. For this theoretical insuccess Marx's theory, although founded on a clear problem and hence naturally aimed at achieving a PO theory composed by DNPs, AAAs and the application of the PSR, never was accomplished. The same inconclusive theoretical attitude was in Basaglia, who already lacked of a clear PO theory of a therapeutic work. His adhesion to Marx's theory added an inconclusive theory in formulating a PO theory; the two insufficiencies aggravated his effort for progressing in his theoretical search.

5. The relationship between a mental patient and a psychiatric institution

First of all one has to consider what kind of conflict a total institution represents for a mental patient. A total institution is based on A (assumptions of juridical nature and social power) which do not recognize any other possible motivation; so that the mental patient has to accept as absolute impositions these motivations, translated in regulations, orders, and the wills of the representative of the institution, i.e. therapists and nurses. On the other hand, a total institution does not manifest any feeling C, whereas its behavior B is inscrutable or however outside the control of a mental patient. In sum, in this conflictual relationship a total institution only acts as an A. Let us consider now patient's side. His motivations A are unknown to himself; his feelings C are a storm, whereas his behavior B is not under his control so that he is not aware of what he is doing. In sum, a mental patient only lives a tormenting C, whereas he is acting according to an uncontrolled B (without referring to A, whatever its content). Hence, the two actors of the conflict are at all severed: the institution presents only A, whereas the mental patient only B and C. No worst situation may occur, i.e. to live in distinct dimensions of a common conflict. This kind of abnormal life was possible since the institution imposed to a mental patient so much oppressive relationships of social power (A) that he had no possibility of changing his situation.

Face a so authoritarian institution the immediate reaction of a humanistic therapist is of course the determination of abolishing it. *The istituzione negata* (The denied institution) was the title of a celebrated book edited by Basaglia; it also became the most famous slogan linked to his work.

Moreover, the *La negazione del ruolo* (The denial of the social role) was a basic point of this movement that wanted to change the institutionalized work in the psychiatry of the mental ill persons.

But what after the negation of the existing institutions and the pre-established roles? In order to overcome the forced life inside an authoritarian institution of mental hospital Basaglia's strategy was to parallel to Freud's therapeutic process of healing a Patient. First of all he recovered the interpersonal relationships. The mental patient's B was educated (leaving apart his sanitization through psychotropic drugs) to cohabit within a community and even the social environment of town's life, so much to be trained to communicate as much as possible. Moreover, the patient was empowered of communicating his C to a human being (therapist); who answered by trying to adhere to Patient's feelings so much to lead his C to converge to the latter's C. Eventually, the therapist tried to discover the A of the mental patient. In sum, the therapist put himself at the service of the mental patient in order to recover his personality endowed of an entire triad A-B-C and leads him to approach the unity of his personality.

But, owing to the insufficiencies of the theories at his disposal, Basaglia's therapeutic path was more a step-after-step experiment rather than a theorized program; in particular in his analyses the DNPs, the AAAs and the application of the PSR remained ignored.

In sum, Basaglia elicited a great, enormous effort for changing a very hard social situation by means of weak forces as the work from the bottom of a minority is. But, since all his theoretical frameworks (phenomenology, implicit Galtung A-B-C and Marx's theory) were not completed frameworks, the result of his effort left great open problems. To

which Basaglia, fearing at all moment political ebb, at last answered by taking extreme positions.

The problem that Basaglia's work poses to us does not consist, like a naive (or mischievous naive) reading could make us believe, in his renunciation of the therapeutic dimension. The difficulties instead born from the extremism of his therapeutic approach: it is possible to continue to escape indefinitely every form of knowledge and institutional organization in order to guarantee the therapeutic nature of the situation? And if this is not possible, like Basaglia himself admits, will be completely influential the type of knowledge and the kind and institutional organization which will come to replace the traditional ones, and from which then it will be necessary tear again? Is it completely irrelevant that Italian psychiatry functions today, concretely, towards a certain theoretical and technical armamentarium rather than another? On which models does it work today Italian territorial psychiatry? English, French, American or others? Uncritical identification of own role with the practical-political dimension as far as an absolute guarantee of an infinite suspension of the role itself — does not actually serve to prevent any debate on the concrete institutional functioning of these new models? In other words, therapist's feeling of being a militant does not also serve to conceal his own technical function, which thus comes to be imposed surreptitiously? Especially this function, by identifying with the "political vocation" of the alternative psychiatrists, does tend to solve the psychiatric problem through a new form of technicality of legal, political and administrative nature?²³.

²³ Ivi, p. 205 (My translation in English language). This page constitutes the end of the chap. 4: *The freedom's laboratory*.